

Exploring the use of cohesive devices in writing among secondary-level learners of Chinese: a corpus study

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The purpose of the study is to investigate how secondary-level (6th, 8th, and 9th grades) learners of Chinese from Utah Dual Language Immersion (DLI) programs use cohesive devices in their writing production. In Chinese, cohesive devices (e.g., conjunctive adverbs and conjunctions) can be used to connect words, phrases, clauses, and sentences. This study will focus on cohesive devices that connect clauses and sentences, which make learners' written text fluent and cohesive. Previous research found that the appropriate use of cohesive devices can improve second language learners' writing performance in terms of coherence and comprehensibility (Ke, 2005; Xiao, 2010). In addition, according to ACTFL proficiency guidelines for writing (American Council on the Teaching of Foreign Languages, 2012), learners should be able to produce connected sentences at the intermediate level; connected discourse of paragraph length and structure is required for learners at an advanced level. Therefore, learning to use cohesive devices to connect sentences is essential for learners to improve their Chinese proficiency.

The researcher will analyze the Chinese sub-corpus of Written Corpus of Utah Dual Language Immersion (Corpus of Utah Dual Language Immersion [CUDLI], n.d.), a corpus of written responses to the presentational writing portion of the ACTFL Assessment of Performance toward Proficiency in Languages (AAPPL). The Chinese sub-corpus contains data from 12,467 students from Chinese DLI programs and 47,988 text files. The analysis will focus on the frequency, variety, and accuracy of cohesive devices learners use in each grade. Then the study will investigate if learners progress using cohesive devices and how they improve. The results will be presented via descriptive statistics.

Regarding pedagogical implications, the study will provide suggestions to Chinese DLI teachers on how to help learners improve their writing proficiency. According to the result, the teacher can improve their teaching methods in classes, such as teaching cohesive devices explicitly, giving more corrective feedback on cohesive devices, and adjusting the writing prompts.

References

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